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Living with Risks:

Sharing the Good Practice

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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**All of papers in this Proceedings are reviewed under control of Scientific
Committee of 30th Annual Conference of Society for Risk Analysis – Europe:
Living with Risks – Sharing the Good Practice**

Society for Risk Analysis – Europe and Disaster Risk Management Centre, Faculty of Technical Sciences, University of Novi Sad, organize 30th Annual Conference with the general subject “Living with Risks – Sharing the Good Practice”.

The scientist and risk professionals from all areas were invited to share their knowledge and experience of applied risk analysis and science, including risk assessment, risk characterization, risk perception, risk communication, risk management, risk governance and policy, relating to risks which are of concern to individuals, organizations in the public and private sector, or to society at local, regional, national, or global levels.

This conference, as well as the previous ones, contribute from all fields dealing with risk: Environment, Disaster Risk Reduction, Fire Safety, Health and Safety at Work, Urban Safety and Security, Insurance and Finance, Project Management Risks, Cyber Security, Terrorism and all other risk topics from practice.

Members of the International Scientific Committee actively participated in the preparation of the conference, both as reviewers and authors. Annual meetings/conferences are an opportunity for risk analysts to come together to discuss issues, problems, goals and future research questions. New areas for risk analysis are emerging and new disciplines are contributing to the ongoing debate about risk analysis in its various facets.

This year the authors from 27 countries participate in the conference, and the Book of abstracts contain 116 abstracts. The editors are sincerely grateful to all the authors for the contribution to this event.

Editors

The Republic of Serbia response to the global public health crisis Covid 19 and socio-economic impact of the event

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Abstract

The beginning of 2020 started with global public health crisis caused by a pandemic of a virus called Corona 19. Life began to take place in extraordinary conditions for which the society was not adequately prepared. At the end of the first quarter of 2020, a state of emergency was declared in the Republic of Serbia due to the health crisis. Measures to combat the epidemic which the state has declared, have reduced economic and social life to a minimum. Within two years more than 80 regulations have been adopted of which half in the period of emergency state. The paper will present the measures taken by the Government of the Republic of Serbia in order to fight and suppress the infection in short time. Then, how the local governments managed the crisis through the civil protection system, which contributed to overcoming adverse events more easily. Also, the paper will present the socio - economic impact of the epidemic on Serbia and analyze were the national measures adequate.

Key words: *pandemic, risk reduction, global crisis, socio-economic impact, Covid 19.*